

ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-PROFESSIONAL PROBLEMS FACING THE INSPECTORS OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN DR CONGO THROUGH GOPP

Corneille Luboya Tshiunza^{1,2,i},

Denis Shanga Kapinga³,

Alhaji Bakar Kamara¹

¹School of Education, Central China Normal University,
Wuhan, China

²Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences,
National Pedagogical University,
Kinshasa, DR Congo

³Chief of Educational Province of Congo Central II,
Mbanza-Ngungu, DR Congo

Abstract:

In Democratic Republic of the Congo, the body of school inspectors aims at controlling and evaluating the pedagogic, administrative and financial of school activities. They observe, assess, and advise the school employees with improving mechanisms of school performance and teaching quality. Due to the shortage of school inspectors (109 teachers of secondary schools for 1 inspector), many schools do not receive the control and supervision. However, in their routine works, the roving inspectors are facing some problems. These problems have affected negatively the effectiveness of their school inspection. This study aims at identifying and categorizing the problems which the school inspectors are facing during their socio-professional career. The survey was conducted by questionnaire (administered in a Stratified Sampling weighted consisting of 200 inspectors) and data analyzed by the analysis of content and statistical analysis. The findings indicated the inspection relative to control of education is more frequent than internal administration, on-the-job training and evaluation or testing. In this school inspection sessions, the problems of social life conditions, the technical and the working conditions are more significant than the contextual problems. The school inspectors have proposed possible solutions to solve these challenges through GOPP.

Keywords: problem, teaching inspector, education inspection and pool of school inspection, GOPP

ⁱ Correspondence: email corneilleluboya@outlook.fr

1. Introduction

Since more than two decades, in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), although an educational system is organized, with the stakeholders claim about the decline in the quality of education, while there are control structures of teaching-learning activities in the national schools. This decline of education quality questions the missions and effectiveness of the inspection services and the work of inspectors. It should be noted that in DRC, the school inspection was ever born since colonial times, precisely December 25, 1926, under the leadership of colonial Belgian. Education inspection has instituted by order No. 129 / S.G which determines the responsibilities of the inspector general of the primary, secondary and professional education. The Education Inspection Department is consisting on 90 years of existence. It includes five (5) following periods: (i) re-foundation of the inspection (1960-1964); (ii) stimulus period (1964-1967); (iii) Outreach period (1967-1978); (iv) restructuring period (1978) and revitalize take-off period (v). Every period has its strengths and limits.

Many studies were conducted on the occupations or professions of the Inspectors of education. Koyagbia (2007-2008) concluded that teachers of the Gombe pool feel supervised and controlled by the inspectors. The supervision of teachers by the inspectors is realized in the form of pedagogical training sessions. These actions of training focus on preparing a lesson, using techniques and methods of teaching. Nakasila (2007-2008) also concluded similarly on the superiority of the pedagogical inspection on others (training, administrative, evaluation). Bipungame (2007-2008) noted that in Ngaliema Pool Inspection, the number of roving inspectors is normal than national standard, or 22 in total. As for the real qualitative needs, this pool inspection needed 4 roving inspectors additional as the quantitative need cannot cover the qualitative need. On this, the qualitative need is estimated at 34 inspectors. Tshituala (2007-2008) concluded that there is the need for secondary education inspectors in the inspection pool of Kimbanseke. There are also some challenges in this inspection pool notably working conditions and lack number of the inspectors for inspection of classes and teachers. The need to provide adequate material resources and recruitment and training of the inspectors are one of the priorities. In their journey work, the teaching inspectors are faced by the material, technical and socio-economic difficulties. Few studies were focused in the problems faced by these actors of effectiveness and control quality of schools (Ndandula, 2008).

In DRC, social and working conditions of the Inspectors are no appreciable. The study approaches the inspectors by survey and analysis the social-professional challenges facing during their career or experiences. This study brings some light on the factors which are affected the process of teaching quality and working conditions of the inspectors. This study is aimed to collect the views of the inspectors on the exercise of their professional duties, to grasp the problems which the inspectors are facing in the workplace and address the perspectives for improvement of conditions of social life, technical and material of work and the strengthening of the capacity of inspectors. This study tries to answer the following questions:

- What are the perceptions of school inspectors about the conditions and context in which they exercise their professional activities?
- What are the components of problems facing the inspectors in exercising of their profession?
- What the module of school inspection are more exploiting throughout the school inspection activities?
- What perspectives of inspection problems do inspectors offer to the authorities of DRC education system?

2. Theoretical Foundation

This point defines Problem, Teaching Inspector, Education Inspection and Pool of School Inspection, GOPP and describes theoretical and DRC legal framework of education inspection.

2.1. Definitions and Discussion of Concepts

2.1.1. Problem

According to the Encyclopedic Universal Dictionary (2009, p.976), a problem is “a question to be solved according to a set of data in a science. The dictionary le Robert (1967, p.910) sheds new light in the definition of the problem, noting that it is “*a matter to resolve which lends to discussion in a science*”. Masamba (2012, p.19) estimate that “*the problem is a gap between a current situation which must be changed and a goal achieve, or between a situation unsatisfactory and another desirable situation*”. The problem is, indeed, a matter or question to be resolved, an obscure point proposed to clarify (Luboya, 2014). There are several meanings of the concept problem: (i) a problem is a gap between the ideal and the real situation or experienced in the field; (ii) a problem is a real difficulty experienced field and to which the researcher wants to give an answer. It should be noted that field can be the school, the company, the hospital, the field, the parish according to the field of research; and (iii) a problem is a bitter acknowledgement of a situation experienced by the researcher in the field.

From our understanding, the problem arises as a dead end to face and which must be overcome to ensure effectiveness and efficiency in the expectation of the goals that you set for the execution of a task. Here, the term problem refers to the difficulties experienced by the inspectors in their actions which we want to collect, identify, categorize and study and solve. It is important to say that working in a difficult context offers no possibility to prove excellence. Inspectors must be accompanied in their work so that they produce the best of themselves.

2.1.2. Inspector of Education

To better understand the concept of education inspector, it is important to define the term Inspector individually. The Robert (1998, p.916), sets the Inspector as being “the person who is responsible to monitor a work, to control the operation of a service, to ensure the application of the regulations, he/she is a controller. The Little Larousse

illustrated (1957, p.327), meanwhile, is considered a title given to officers of various utilities and some general officers of a mission of monitoring and control.

Of the foregoing, is considered as a teaching Inspector, says Ndandula (2008), any person mandated by the State and which is responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of such teaching activities as carried out at the level of the school. The term Inspector corroborates in Counsellor of education depending on the environment. Some countries recognize through the Inspector, the quality of the school counselor or teaching. A successful education is to ensure a competent, impartial, staff in teaching techniques. These men, noted Dottrens (1961), are none other than education inspectors, who are best educators and teachers, experienced and highly located in the teaching of education of a country and administrative hierarchy.

In DRC, the monitoring and control of teaching preschool, primary, secondary and professional schools are provided by the school inspectorate and school leaders. Then the function of an inspector is to control, to evaluate and train, the researchers found wise to investigate them because of their power to enjoy the educational institutions. The Inspector, through its administrative position and rank which it is clothed in the administration, is before all a superior officer to check, stimulate and control the work of teachers. Therefore, the Inspector is a liaison officer in the center of the groups participating in education (State, Family and Teacher). These conditions made the school counselor become a guide and a companion of work who understands the difficulties of teaching. He becomes the technician who provides the means to overcome the obstacles, a moderator who informs the new processes and suggest the necessary teaching skills. It is in this way he will take or complete the mission assigned to him by the society: *"being the educator of educators who observes, compares, appreciate, suggests, inspires and protects"*.

The Inspector is not only the supervisor of teachers or the controller of the State, but he is also the representative of families who take it gladly for arbitrage. He is a liaison officer at the crossroads of the educational forces. Given its function, it can become for some and for others, a catalyst whose presence and action facilitate happy reactions to the State and childhood by the control he exercises and the improvements it offers teachers and parents. The Inspector of education gives confidence and security to both supervisors and teachers, representatives of the family and the State. It must become a magistrate of education. It represents the general interest of the society in opposition to special interests that can show parents, teachers and children.

2.1.3. Pool of School Inspection

Pool of School Inspection is a group of officers who exercise an activity within a company. It is a division of social, political, administrative professional, cultural, which gives a breakdown of people, agents or actors grouped together, forming a more or less balanced number of individuals. This term can also mean a radius of action, an entity that is part of an administration (DR Congo-MINEPS, 2012).

A pool of school inspection is a division of the school inspection in DR Congo established at the level of each district according to the administrative-territorial

country division. It is usually of the Inspectorate General of education (IGE), the provincial Inspection (PPI) and the inspection pool (INSPOOL). In each pool inspection, there are a corps of roving inspectors, headed by a Chief Inspector of pool, whose number varies according to the needs and specialties.

The INSPOOL is the real entity where the inspectors' agents are men of field closest to the base, i.e. schools and teachers. In order to avoid duplication, each pool inspection has under its supervision a determined number of schools located in some district. In the city of Kinshasa, there are three representations of school inspection and each provincial inspection includes several inspection pools: (i) Provincial Inspection (PPI) Kinshasa - East; (ii) Provincial Inspection of Kinshasa-Center; and (iii) Provincial Inspection of Kinshasa-West.

2.1.4. Goal Oriented Project Planning (GOPP)

With its experience and awareness of the mediocrity of the results of the actions already undertaken, the German Technical assistance Agency (GTZ) proposed, in the beginning of the years 80, a systematic model of project planning in order to remedy the Major planning problem (Lohmeier, 1997). The GOPP (Goal Oriented Project Planning) in English and PIPO or PPOO (respectively Project Planning by Objectives or Planning of Interventions by Objectives) in French is often used in three stages: construction of problem tree, construction of solution tree and the logical framework of the project. In this study, we apply two first steps. Firstly, we interviewed the inspectors about their challenges, problems and difficulties of social life and working conditions. We discuss the possible causes of the central problem and other related problems, the potential effects of this central problem or the consequences and redefine or reformulate the problems and discard the unreal or imagined problems. We ask for the causes of the central problem. Secondly, we ask the Inspectors to formulate the solutions in terms of the objectives or the tree of the action objectives to solve the problems identified. This is the definition of each problem (central problem, causes and consequences) in terms of solution. The description of the future situation is reached after the solution of the problems or after the improvement of the situation. The solution to the central problem is the objective; the solution to a cause is a means and the solution for a consequence is a goal.

2.2. Theoretical and Legal Framework of Education Inspection in DR Congo

2.2.1. Legal Foundation of Education Inspection in DR Congo

Champy and Eteve (1994, p.536) stated that the inspection is a control activity and assessment of the functioning of the educational system. It takes various forms depending on the periods and countries: its functions, its forms, its modalities of exercise are highly dependent on the administrative organization of teaching.

In DR Congo, it is the framework law No. 14/004 of 11 February 2014 national education, in its section 4, where it talks about the Inspection of education. Article 145 stipulates: *"the public institutions or private accredited maternal, primary, secondary and*

vocational education are subject to the pedagogical, administrative, and financial and health control modalities determined by regulation”.

The control of pre-school, primary, secondary and professional education (EPSP) as well as training teachers and teaching evaluation are exercised by the body of inspectors. The body of inspectors within maternal, primary, secondary and vocational education is governed by the status of staff of career of public services of the State. It reports to the Minister of the maternal, primary, secondary and vocational education. The Organization and functioning of this body are set by Decree of the Prime Minister deliberated in the Council of Ministers (Article 146). The body of inspectors of education in DR Congo is governed by legal texts below: (i) Law No. 81-003 of 17 July 1981, on the status of the staff of career services of the State, especially articles 1, 5 and 15; (ii) Ordinance No. 78-096 March 02, 1987, regulation of Directors relative to the teaching staff of the Ministry of the PSB; (iii) Ordinance No. 78-375 of 6 September 1978, regulation of administration of body of inspectors of the EPSP.

2.2.2. Mission and Role of the Inspector

Ravez (2016) states that the main tasks of the inspectors are to work until the schools will meet education requirements. This includes determining if studies are at a sufficient level, and if approved, the “*organizing power*” programs are monitored. To exercise this control mission, he insists, the inspectors may attend classes, ask students, review their work, take knowledge of the documents that is required, and visit the schools. They shall, however, refrain from making guidelines for teaching methods: they are left to the initiative of organizing powers. Inspectors are nevertheless called to make sure the animation of the pedagogical teams, organize or supervise the in-service training of teachers and in the technical field, to establish a permanent collaboration with professional social circles.

In DRC, alternatively to the framework law No. 14/004 of 11 February 2014 national education, the role and mission of the Inspector are explicitly defined by the regulatory voice. It's Ordinance No. 73/023 of July 4, 1973, on the status of the staff of career of public services of the State, especially in its articles 1 and 5 such that reviewed and amended by Ordinance No. 75/404 of 4 December 1975 on administrative regulation on the teaching staff of the Department of the EPSP, especially in its articles 2.3 and 10 paragraphs 1 which specifies that it is created in the Department of the EPSP a body of specialized agents known as body of inspectors of the EPSP. This body is responsible for control and to promote national education and school education (Articles 1 and 2).

In this purpose, the body of inspectors has four roles and missions including : (i) Control through the school inspections in pedagogic, administrative and financial fields; (ii) observe, assess, advise the school staff and teachers and control its level of their performance, evaluate the teaching quality in schools, in the light of the curricula and objectives set by the State, organizing power; (iii) to report to the supervisor and make in account the results of his mission as well to the national authorities that the Department, and both at the central and provincial levels and (iv) to make concrete

propositions regarding remedies to apply to defective situations and to propose improvements.

In order to accomplish its missions, inspectorates of education need the material and human resources. In terms of human resources, the inspection is currently 66 roving inspectors for the pre-school, 408 for primary and secondary 1 650. Put in relation to the number of teachers, the number of roving inspectors gives teachers ratios: Inspector of 102: 1 for kindergarten, 566: 1 for primary and 109: 1 for secondary schools, (Report of the Inspectorate General, 2014).

Consequently, the inspection does not yet of sufficient staff resources for the effective fulfilment of its mission. Because, if he spends a day at the visit of a teacher, an Inspector of the kindergarten has need of two months and a half to cover all teachers and all classes under his charge. It is similar to the inspectors of secondary schools. On the other hand, the inspector of the primary school needs a year and a half for the performance of the same work. Apart from the lack of human resources, service control and evaluation also suffers from the narrowness of the budget which is allowed. Thus, it is the teachers and schools in rural areas mainly, who spend several years without the benefit of these technicians of education visits. Because they do not enjoy themselves adequate training, inspectors often indulge in more administrative controls and educational (Mokonzi et al, 2009).

Because of the lack of adequate financial resources, control arrangements that the inspection is in principle called to fill is not used wisely. Indeed, the controls provided by the Inspectorate are not performing systematically. Those admitted to the body of inspectors must in principle have passed with satisfaction a special competition and appropriate training for a period of six months. The regulations have made Inspector of education, to go through a competition. The special competition has 3 parts: the first part is a review in the school administration including pedagogy, financial administration and school hygiene. The second part concerns the oral test and covers some issues not to mention those related to pedagogy. The third part is a practical test administered by the State of the Ministry of Primary, secondary and Professional Education. In addition to the selected conditions, the candidate is subject to probation by the State Commission of E.P.S.P.

Between 1980 and 1990, the training of inspectors was provided by the Training Institute of Management Education (IFCE) based in Kisangani, capital of Oriental Province of DR Congo. Following the stopping of funding by donors, including UNESCO, from 1990-1991, the Institute has ceased its operation, particularly those that relate to the training of inspectors. Also currently, inspectors undergo on-the-job training which turns the rest largely insufficient in the light of the tasks required by their mission (Mokonzi et al, 2009).

2.2.3. Disciplinary System, Evaluation of Performance and Promotion of the Inspector

The Ordinance No. 75/404 of 4 December 1975 law teachers of the Department of the PSB, especially in its articles 14 and 15 States that in addition to the disciplinary regime for the teaching staff, the following disciplinary penalties are applicable to inspectors:

(i) the call to order; (ii) a reprimand; (iii) the disciplinary move and (iv) the revocation or fire.

Any inspector who will have the mention “good” successively must be retrained by the Minister of the EPSP. If after next two years, he is unable to get mention “very good”, this inspector will be excluded automatically from the body of inspectors. This exclusion results in the loss of quality of Inspector and the assignment to other duties, (Article 15).

How can we assess the performance of the inspectors? In General, inspectors are assessed by the teachers themselves by their testimony. But the testimony of teachers are not always objective. The inspection authorities assess the merits of the school inspectors through the direct and indirect criteria as follow: (i) In the teaching field (authorities can evaluate the value of their projects); (ii) in scientific field (their research, publications, and collaboration attitude) and (iii) in the administrative area (bonds, punctuality in administrative correspondence, send the requested documents, accuracy and speed in their reports, interest and how to deal with difficult cases).

From roving the itinerant Inspector of pre-school, primary and secondary education to rank of regional inspector or head of pool, the inspector must be able to exercise its function more or less 5 years. If there are several candidates of same experience year, age and same education level, the selection will be made in order of merit. The Inspector General is designated from among the Deputy Inspectors General. The EPSP Minister determines by order the areas of action of inspectors, their scope and their delivery. It ensures continuous training to make them better able to control and evaluate the teaching. It will create within the corps of inspectors, specialty services and engineering offices (Ordinance-Law No. 75/404 of 4 December 1975).

2.2.4. Function of Inspector

A danger which is threatening the Congolese school is that of a divorce between the old and the young teachers. There is also the danger between qualified teachers and unqualified teachers, a danger of misunderstanding the consequences could be severe for unit of pedagogical actions. Ndandula (2008) believes that the new school needs new teachers. It calls for the transformation of the institutions dedicated to the training of the teaching staff. Hence, efforts in several countries to better equip inspectors because progress of education from quality and quantity aspects requires those who are responsible to follow the evolution of science dealing with the child and social life, improve their methods of teaching, they know the result of other educators in order to adapt to their condition of work experiences that have succeeded and that they cannot ignore.

In RDC as in other countries of the world, the tasks and responsibilities of a teacher are binding, it can be to prepare lessons, animate them, fix the various works, so managing the class on a daily basis. All these obligations prevent the teacher to renew the content and form of what he gained in school during his training.

In addition, some teachers are far from the zone with higher school culture and by their own means can hardly stand abreast of new ideas on the teaching. From this, it

follows very generally that some teachers vegetate and it is important to help them (Ndandula, 2008). This request for assistance expressed or not expressed clearly is the essential task of the Inspector. This aid must not confine itself to spread ideas, to make known the methods but it must be vigilant and attentive in school life, it is a comfort and sympathy. The inspector must play the role of this international radio that brings new information to anywhere in the world. It plays this role not as a robot but as a human with a heart and a head.

Dottrens (1961) notes that the function of the Inspector is above all an educational function, that is, the inspector must have the means which include personal interviews and knowledge of its staff. It is during interviews from man to man (teacher-inspector) that will make him aware of his responsibility, to encourage good initiatives and sometimes corrects errors, stimulates the contribution of each to the general progress of education. In short, inspector influences the educational work. So therefore, this educational function is considered as a control of the levels of teachers in order to train them.

The occasions of educational or pedagogical meeting with teachers of his discipline are a valuable didactic action which must use the Inspector in the exercise of its functions. Meetings should gather after educational inspection of teachers from the same school or several schools visited. It is an opportunity that the Inspector exposes the techniques or methods he suggests, and then will be an exchange of views, resolving difficulties and healthy collaboration settling. Anyone will take a real profit of these discussions between colleagues and learn better the sense of solidarity that unites all employees to the educational mission. It is in this same way that Champy and Eteve (1994) insists that the Inspector suggests; he does not impose. He will be required especially when teaching processes have been proven. He should show why this course of action can be improved and make others of his special knowledge and experiences. This will depend on the attitude of understanding and worthy, as far from the proud complacency, the camaraderie of unholy, both are confidence and esteem.

2.2.5. Working Tools of an Inspector of Education in DR Congo

These working tools in DR Congo are documents or different report cards that the Inspection Services gives to the inspectors. They establish and fill them and report to their superiors about activities which they engaged in the field. Here is a summary of these modules tools:

Table 1 : Different Types of Modules of Inspection

Modules	Forms
I module: Internal Administration (A)	Data sheet (A1), (A2) quarterly Plan activities, the quarterly statement of activities (A3); the annual statement of activities (A4); the statement of absence (A5); the COC (A6); the letters to write and ship (A7): without canvas and other administrative activities (A8): without canvas
Module II : Control of education (C)	First visit (C1); administrative Inspection (C2); educational inspection (C3); financial Inspectorate (C4); Inspection of a Deputy (C5); the investigation (C6); Inspection of record (C7) and other control activities (C8): without canvas.
Module III: On-the-job training (C)	Inspection of training (F1); Action of training (F2); Action of coaching (F3); Training tool (F4) and other training activities (F5): without canvas.
Module IV: Evaluation or testing (E,T)	Identification of high school finalist (E01); listing of students (E2); list operational (E11); School scores statement (E13); Scores of off-session (E 80) and student cards (E 97)

Source: DR Congo-MINEPS, Modulus of inspectors training (2012).

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

This is an exploratory study using the mixed method. A survey conducted using interviews and questionnaire. An effort of quantitative analysis was carried out to analysis the socio-professional problems facing by the inspectors of secondary schools in DR Congo through PIPO. Qualitative and quantitative data are sequentially used to address the issues highlighted in the study (Luboya, Liu and Eugenio, 2017).

3.2. Participants

The DR Congo has 1 650 for secondary education and in 260 (15.8%) of them from capital city and province of Kinshasa, (DR Congo - Report of the Inspectorate General, 2014-2015). In these 260 of inspectors, we extracted a Stratified Random Sampling of 200 inspectors, or 71, 4% with 95% confidence and 5% according the size and the type of sample which is advising by Mayer and Quellet (1991)

Among the inspectors selected by our sample, men are in the majority (67%), compared to 33 percent of women. the parity is outstanding because of an imbalance, the men far beyond women. Inspectors who have Bachelor's Degree and undergraduates (80%) are more than those (20%) have State Diploma Degree (figure 1A).

Figure 1: Socio-Characteristics of Participants

Source: Authors draw from Survey Data

Thus, most of the inspectors have higher educated level. The majority of surveyed inspectors (67%) have 12 years of working experiences and more; only 20 % of school inspectors have worked between 4 and 11 years and 13 % of them are operating since less than 4 years.

3.3. Data Collection Procedure and Instruments

Regarding strategies and processing of data collection, we used the survey method. The documentary analysis, the questionnaire and the interviews have been used as data collection techniques. The survey process includes two major steps: it is of pre-investigation and the investigation (Cohen, Manion, and Morrison, 2000).

The Pre-Survey: The pre-survey is a step in the research work that precedes the survey. In this step, we have developed the first version of questionnaire and submitted it to 11 inspectors to test the reliability, accuracy and the unidimensional of our questionnaire. The results achieved at this stage allowed us to correct the deficiencies experienced by the subjects and the revitalization of the questionnaire. The consistency and the validity of our final questionnaire were tested with the coefficient of Alpha of Cronbach (.82), that is to say a very higher significance (.20) of Kuder-Richardson estimated (.77) and the coefficient of variance (1.10).

The Survey: the survey is conducted by the interview and questionnaire administration. During the survey, the researchers conducted the administration of the questionnaire. Directed by Javeau (1986), we used two kinds including: the direct and indirect administration. The first is the interviewee himself notes his answers to the questions, whereas the indirect administration where we notes the answers to the questions the subject interviewed him provided.

The researchers first started by reports of the General Inspectorate 2015-2016, to realize the reality of the Congolese inspection including the number of inspectors. From the beginning of the month of June 2016, we administered our questionnaire in its final version. The total survey took place in two months - the time interval between the beginnings of June until the end of the month of July 2016.

3.4. Management and Analysis of data

The management and data analysis occurred by content analysis. Bardin (1986) states that content analysis is set of the techniques of analysis of communication by systematic procedures and objective description of the content of the messages from the indicators to the lower part of knowledge related to the conditions of production, perception of these messages. Content analysis supposes usually three stages: registration, categorization and quantification. This technique allowed us to strip and treat the answers, arguments or comments of opened and semi-opened questions in our questionnaire and the data from taking notes in interviews: (i) we record the responses to opened-questions and the justifications of the semi-enclosed questions; (ii) next, we identify the responses and categorize them according to the ideas, units and context (here, we have applied the techniques of planning of Interventions by objective, GOPP in its two phases: tree problems and solutions); (iii) And finally, we collect the frequencies of responses in order to quantify them in percent through statistical analysis (calculation of frequencies and percentages).

Furthermore, to test the relation between the socio-professional variables used in our study (level of study, sex and seniority) and the various activities and problems of inspection, we used a nonparametric statistical test. For need of reliability and statistical accuracy, we used SSPS version 22 for all operations of data analysis (Field, 2013).

4. Results

The study presents the findings through the thematic as follow:

4.1. About the Socio-Professional Context of Work of Inspections in Kinshasa

The majority of inspectors (60%) believe that school principals and teachers, are totally willing to be controlled. The minority (40%) justifies their opinions by the attitude and the psychological state of the people visited by inspectors (distrust, anger, contempt, and fear, panic).

Figure 1B: Socio-professional context of work of inspectors

Regarding to the value of the current work of the Inspector, 57% reported that the current work of the Inspector partially retains its value; 30% felt that this value is completely guarded and 13% argued that the current work of the Inspector work

became worthless. We see that the majority (70%) of the Inspectors recognize that their professions or job have not saved all of its value yet as more than next two decades. If all interviewed Inspectors agree on the legal authority of the Inspector to the inspected persons, however all of them are deploying their postures during the visits of inspectors. An inspector (anonymity) said that: *"Although have authority before our subjects to control but we lose our authority and feel generally ridiculous because of financially dependent on those that we control."* and another (anonymity) adds: *"How should we be very stern and strict in our work if we expect them (controlled people) a transport to reach another school or for to return in our pool..."*

4.2. About the Nature and Types of Inspections conducted by Inspector

Out of 100% of the inspectors, 40% were in some schools for more than a year; 27% often arrive in school while 33% visit rarely their schools. We find that the majority of inspectors (73%) do not descend on ground to control school leaders and teachers (table 2).

Table 2: Gender, studies level and working experience and nature and types of inspections

Visit of teaching inspection	Number		%	
Often	54		27	
Sometimes	80		40	
Rarely	66		33	
Total	200		100	
Variables	DII	Chi-Square	Coeff. of Cramer (V)	P-Value
Gender	1	$X^2_c = 2,500$	0,289	0,05 or 5%
Working experience	2	$X^2_c = 2,771$	0,304	
Education	3	$X^2_c = 5,741$	0,437	

Source: Authors draw from survey data

The problems facing inspectors are not significantly influenced by their gender ($X^2_c = 2,500$, $V=0,289$) and working experience ($X^2_c = 2,771$, $V=0,304$). In other words, the problems encountered by the inspectors in the exercise of their profession are not depending on their gender or work experience at the significance level of .025 with the results of V of Cramer close to 0 and less than 1, (either 0,289 or 0,304). In addition, educational level of inspector ($X^2 = 5, 741$, $V=0,437$) have significantly influenced their problems.

Figure 2: Nature and type of inspection activities

When the inspectors arrive in schools to inspect, according to Figure 2, module II is more operated (62%); followed by module IV (20%); Modules I and III share 9% each. This means that the education inspection is the mostly exploited during inspection visits. Inspectors operate more administrative Inspection (C2); Inspection financial (C4), the Inspection of a Deputy (C5), the investigation (C6) and Inspection of record (C7). Among the forms of module II, educational Inspection (C3) is less exploited, and some Inspectors believe that it is avoided because it is demanding and consumes more time in a day of inspection. We can also add the lack of on-the-job training of inspectors. The results ($X^2 = 58.036$, $p = .03$) show the positive significant difference between these differences types of inspections.

4.3. About the Socio-Professional Problems faced by Inspectors, Causes and Consequences

In the current context of profession of inspectors, the majority of inspectors (77%) agreed completely on the difficulties encountered during the inspection actions in schools compared with 23 percent who acknowledged particularly.

Table 3: Gender, education, working experience and socio-professional problems

Visit of teaching inspection	Number	%		
Often Facing challenges	154	77		
Rarely Facing challenges	46	23		
Total	200	100		
Variables	DII	Chi-Square	Coeff. of Cramer (V)	P-Value
Gender	1	$X^2= 0,093$	0,131	0,05 or 5%
Working experience	2	$X^2= 4,258$	0,261	
Education	3	$X^2=0,932$	0,152	

Source: Authors draw from survey data

The problems encountered by the inspectors are not significantly influenced by their genders ($X^2=0,093$, $V=0,131$) and levels of study ($X^2= 0,932$, $V=0,152$). In other words, the difficulties encountered by the inspectors are not depending in their gender or educational level at the significance level of 5% with the results of factor V of Cramer

close to 0 and less than 1. Furthermore, the working experience of inspectors ($X^2 = 4,258$, $V=0,261$) have significantly influenced their experienced problems.

What nature and types of obstacles that inspectors are facing and blocking their ability and effectiveness to produce the work of quality?

According to inspectors as show by figure 3, the problems related to the conditions of life (40%) and material and technical conditions of work (47%) are more frequently and prominent follow-up of those related to the contexts of their professional or job (13%). There is also the positive significant difference between these problems ($X^2 = 43.036$, $p = .000$).

Figure 3: Socio-Professional Problems, Causes et Consequences

In connection with responses to inspectors in this question, we have identified and categorized these problems, their causes and consequences in three groups in a tree of the problems according to the model of GOPP:

The roving inspectors have experienced many problems related to the conditions of social life, their causes and consequences. It is summarizing to the bad condition of work and social life of the inspectors. This central problem is caused by lack of the means of transport and high costs of means of transportation; lack of adequate financial resources to meet the vital needs of their families, school needs of their children and lack of health care; insignificant remuneration; lack of benefit of the legal professional advantages of the inspectors job and professional demotivation are real problems which the inspectors are facing in their careers. These problems and causes detrude the mental and physical health of inspectors, make them feel demotivated and destroy their morality and professional ethics.

About the problems related to material and technical conditions of work, their causes and consequences, the inspectors indicated the bad condition of material and technical work. This central problem is caused by the lack of means for the reproduction of reports; the lack of office supplies and furniture; lack of logistical means for the needs of the service and the lack of technological media and ICT (internet, photocopier machines, typewriter, computers, etc.) for the multiplication of forms and reports of the activities of the inspection, the unavailability of the working tools for the Inspector and lack of free of roaming (inspectors walk and cover the long distances during the inspection visits). They also add lack of canvas of some forms of

inspections and the lack of continuous training of inspectors. Some inspectors do have not the collections of guidelines and official instructions, some administrative documentation and curricula. These problems and causes have as main consequences a bad quality of inspection.

The inspectors are facing various contextual problems during the exercise of their profession. They said the causes and consequences of these problems: imbalance between the number of major of studies provided and the official number authorized, (especially in private schools); period examinations not provided by national school calendar sometimes prevent the fulfillment of some tasks scheduled of the inspectors; the bad reception given to inspectors in some schools and the lack of consideration to inspectors during the inspection visits. In addition, they also report the dismissal of students in their home because of non-payment of school fees prevent educational inspection activities in classroom; the more than official number of students in some schools penalize the realization of educational inspection (C3) and the evaluation of teachers; the depopulation of the semi-rural zone for downtown schools and the proliferation of schools make the area of control of an inspector more vast and difficult to work around; Similarly to the improper allocation of teachers by managers and the pyramid of enrolment in private schools make difficult inspections; the difficulties to reach in some schools being built anarchically; premises of classes not respecting educational standards. Some inspectors add on this list the interpersonal conflict between teachers and school leaders impose inspectors abruptly change the inspection module; the problem of immorality in the workplace and the lack of respect for the teachers to the person of the Inspector also adversely affect the inspection. Some schools lack basic and teaching units cells facilitating the inspection work; some school principals' do not promote continuous training to their assistants and teachers; ignorance of the new curriculum by the majority of teachers and challenges to assessments of the inspectors by the teachers and school leaders.

4.4. Perspectives of Socio-Professional Problems of Inspectors

What perspectives of inspections problems do inspectors give to Congolese education system authorities in the government?

In relation to the notice of roving inspectors on solutions to the problems they are facing, we grouped possible solutions to three groups of objectives, means and finalities. It is shaft solution targets the socio-economic solution tracks (60%), technical and materials tracks (32%) and the political and legal tracks (8%).

The first groups are to improve the conditions of social life of inspectors: health care, compensation, mission expenses, housing, transport and other benefits average; promote and improve the image of an inspector and motivate inspectors regularly by reinforcements (bonuses and awards of excellence).

The second groups are focusing on continuous awareness of the political authorities to the problems of inspection, their causes and consequences; provide inspectors training tools; finance the continuous training of inspectors in the country or abroad; intensify the training seminars tailored to the needs in training inspectors;

provide the adequate material and financial resources to services of inspection; provide the modules, forms, inspections tools and means of transport for the inspection visits; exploit the reports of inspections and create reviews of inspection for the publications of reports and studies related to the activities of school inspections.

The third groups claim for the viability of schools, the recruitment of inspectors and their initial training, opening a center of training of inspectors, provide free education for all, control the respect of guidelines, standards, and laws on the creation of a school, school infrastructure construction, apply the results of studies of the school map, the creation of the cells base and teaching units in schools, provide to inspectors, teachers et school principal the curriculum, the guidelines and official instructions and provide the training to school employees in accordance with training needs.

5. Discussion

5.1. What are the finding of this study compared to other studies?

The results of survey show that inspectors do their jobs in a socio-professional context of difficulty. The majority of the Inspectors recognize that their professions or job lose completely all of its value since the last two decades. And their actions of inspections take power over their legal authorities. This decline of effectiveness of the inspectors' job is also experienced in the various problems encountered by the inspectors.

Most of the inspectors do not descend regularly in schools to inspect or control. This result was similar to that of the study of Nakasila (2007-2008). The basic reason was found by Bipungame (2007-2008), who concludes that there are the real qualitative needs of inspectors. They also have difficulties in means of conveyance to cover school cards. However, in their occasional visit and control of inspection, teachers and local school authorities are totally willing to control and evaluate. But, despite their availability to be controlled, these people display a posture of distrust, anger, contempt, fear, panic and frustrated in front of inspectors. Among all of inspection modules of schools operation, the Inspectors are exploited more significantly in the module of the inspection of education such as administrative Inspection; Inspection financial, the Inspection of a school principal assistants, the investigation and Inspection of record in module II compared to other modules (I, III and IV) provided. These results are similar to those found by Nakasila (2007-2008) and Mokonzi et al, (2009) also state that because the inspectors do not enjoy themselves adequate training, some inspectors engaged more often in more administrative controls than teaching or pedagogical inspection.

During the exercise of their profession, most of inspectors interviewed affirm completely they encountered several problems. According to these inspectors, problems related to social life conditions and material and technical conditions of work are more frequent and prominent compared to the contextual problems. Our further analysis of these results confirms the positive significant difference between these problems. Face to these various problems, its causes and consequences, interviewed inspectors have proposed possible solutions. It is about the possible solutions towards the socio-economic aspects; technical tracks and political and legal tracks of these problems, their

causes and consequences. Some of these tracks have been proposed in the work of Tshituala (2007-2008) and as Ndandula (2008) says "*the new school needs of new teachers*". It calls for the transformation of the institutions dedicated to the training and mentoring of body of new teachers". So, why the several countries make a lot of efforts to give the effective equipment to their teaching inspectors in order to perform their function properly in control, monitoring, training and guide of teachers of national school. Without these efforts, the largest terminal consequence is the decline in the level of national education.

5.2. What are the implications of the variables exploited?

Among the targeted variables (gender, age and educational level), it should be noted regardless of gender or work experience, in majority, the Inspectors believe that visited staff (school management members or teachers) are willing to control and evaluate. Really there is a problem of education level of inspectors. The golden rule is that the inspector must have a higher educational level or equal to that of the people inspected. Often some inspectors encounter resistance from the people inspected due to inadequacy in education level between the Inspector and the teacher or head of the school (state diploma or undergraduate for example). That is why some inspectors are avoided to control some teachers who have a higher level of education than them. Certain inspectors prefer to avoid other modules of inspections. Thus, the acceptance of power, authority and the right of inspectors to monitor and assess a teacher or head of the school depending on the superiority or equality of the educational levels of both parties. In other words, the more an inspector has a higher level of education or equal to the teacher or school management members, stronger is his power, authority and the right to inspect (evaluate, control, guide) except due to some factors such as denial and indiscipline of the teacher, incompetence, lack of know-how and weak personality of the Inspector.

Regarding the problems encountered by the inspectors, these problems do not depend to gender or level of education of the inspectors. In other words, inspectors (man or woman) have the same difficulties or are facing the same problems in the exercise of their profession or mission in schools. These differences are eminent in different educational levels (state diploma, undergraduate or bachelor's degrees). But, these problems depend on the working experience or seniority of inspectors. In other words, inspectors with more seniority or work experience most know the realities and situations-problems with the function of Inspector and logically provided the richest information. And those inspectors have more faced the problems of social life conditions than other problems. They are more adapted in their social-professional context. For example, the less work experience quoted more problems contextual, new zeal to be Inspector prevents them to see their social life conditions or material and technical conditions of work of their job, while in the content of the responses of inspectors who have more working experience; we found three types of problems. This conclusion is established with the significant confidence of the results (See tables 2 and 3).

5.3. What is the originality of research findings?

Our study makes two major contributions:

Theoretically, this study informs DRC stakeholders, school leaders, teachers and inspectors on the school legislative framework whose inspectors or inspection body are operating in regard to missions, roles, discipline system, assessments, evaluation of performance, function, qualities and tools and duties of an inspector or inspection. This study provides information on the perception of inspectors on the value, power, authority and image of their profession or job in accordance with those that are supposed to be controlled, monitored, supervised, and evaluated. This study shows the nature of the activities of inspections and the typology of the problems actually experienced by the inspectors during their inspection activities in schools. It describes and categorizes the difficulties experienced during the inspection, including, in order of importance, the problems or difficulties related to the conditions of social life, material and technical conditions of work and contextual problems, their causes et consequences and some possible solutions.

Practically, the authorities of DRC education system could refer to the results of this study as guideline of their actions in objective to remedy the difficulties that plague the work, profession and function of inspectors, in consequence the quality of inspector work and quality of national teaching.

5.4. What are the limitations of the study and research perspectives?

The study recognizes that the size of the sample of this study limits the possibilities of generalizing the results to the entire body of inspectors of the city province of Kinshasa or DR Congo. 71% of secondary education inspectors cannot allow us to make statistical inferences tending to generalize results from our study nor to the inspectors all the city province Kinshasa, nor from those of the other provinces of the country. Several longitudinal and transversal studies on this topic deserve to be conducted at the pre-school and primary levels in Kinshasa and all the provinces of the DR Congo. The quantitative studies linking socio-professional issues of the inspectors, the performance of teachers and students are also encouraged.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study identifies, categorize and hierarchize the difficulties or problems that inspectors of secondary education are facing in the exercise of their functions or professions, its causes, consequences and propose possible solutions.

The Inspectors of secondary education in Kinshasa (Capital City of DR Congo) do not descend regularly in school to inspect (control, monitoring, evaluating and guiding of quality of teaching and school administration, management and governance operation). During the occasional inspection, school principals, school staff and teachers are available and agree with control. Their availability would be binding by the School Laws, rather than real voluntary availability. In inspection activities of schools operation, the Inspectors exploited significantly the module of the inspection of

education than other inspection modules. Therefore, the forms such as administrative Inspection; Inspection financial, the Inspection of school principal assistants, the investigation and Inspection of record are often preferred

If the inspector profession has lost its value in recent decades, their power or authority remains in front of the school employees to inspect because of the inspected people are afraid of the School Law sanctions. The education level of inspectors increases the acceptance of power, authority and the right of inspectors to monitor and assess a school employee. The more the inspectors have the higher level of education or equal to the school employees, the more stronger is their power, authority and the right to inspect (evaluate, control, guide) in the particular case.

In generally case, the loss of value of inspector job and deterioration of the image of the school inspectors are also explained by several problems that inspectors are facing in the exercise of their profession. These problems make national teaching inspection ineffective and are classified into three categories. However, the problems related to social life conditions and the material and technical working conditions are more significant than the contextual problems. These problems or difficulties do not depend on gender or educational levels of the inspectors. However, they are experienced differently according to the work experience of the inspectors.

Face to these mentioned problems, causes and consequences, some possible solutions are proposed. It is proposed to the authorities of inspection department and the DRC Government to review the financial and material resources allocated to education in order to address priority issues of conditions of social life and the material and technical conditions of inspectors' works in promoting the profession of the Inspectors. This will completely restore their authority; enhance the quality and efficiency of their work that will result to quality national teaching or school performance.

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